

Muyassarkhan Achildieva -

Fargona State University

"Faculty of Arts"

teacher of music education

Farangis Ikromova-

Fergana State University

Faculty of "Art Studies".

Direction "Musical education".

3rd year student.

[*feya.01.m@gmail.com*](mailto:feya.01.m@gmail.com)

Abstract: The article provides information on the work of Halima Nosirova, a bright representative of the Uzbek national opera art. Opinions and comments on the art of Uzbek opera are reflected in the article.

Keywords: national opera, art, musical score, musical memory, psychological interpretation, logical emphasis, lamentation, song, aria, song.

Menga hayot edi siz aytgan "Bayot",

Siz-buyuk xonanda, men-cho 'pon bola.

Mening yuragimda qoldi umrbod,

O'sha oqshomdagi nay bilan nola.

Jamal Kamal

In Uzbekistan, the genre of opera was created on the basis of the development of Uzbek musical drama in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. This was influenced by foreign classical opera, and the arrival of Georgian, Italian, Tatar, Russian and Azerbaijani opera troupes in 1907-1915 and the opening of the Russian Opera Theater in 1918 led to the establishment of opera art, which became an important layer of world music art. At the same time, the services of great teachers such as Muhiddin Qori Yaqubov, Halima Nasirova,

Karim Zakirov, Saodat Qabulova, who are bright representatives of the Uzbek opera art with their unique voices, are incomparable in the development of this art. They left a huge creative legacy and brought the art of Uzbek national opera to the whole world.

Halima Nosirova is one of the owners of such unique voices. You say that no one knows the name of this person... He is well known not only in our republic, but also in many foreign countries. A great artist, a harbinger of freedom, a singer of a new life, an example of the dreams and happiness of many Uzbek women, Halimakhanim, one of the first artists who flew to the stage enjoying the glory of the revolution, closely connected her whole life and creative pursuits with Uzbek opera. He became one of the founders of the opera and ballet theater named after Alisher Navoi.

Halima Nosirova has a strong and attractive, sharp and impressive, juicy and wide-range soprano voice, the owner of an incomparable talent and high skill. You will be amazed at his musical memory, his mastery of scores and his ability to get into the spirit of his characters. The images created by the artist are still distinguished by their originality, sharpness of characters, deep psychological interpretation. This creator left a deep mark in the hearts of our people as a great and experienced representative of Uzbek opera art. It served as a real golden bridge in the subtle and natural combination of two different styles - Uzbek national and European art. This, in turn, opened the way for the national audience to listen to and receive such a complex art form as opera. A highly talented Halima Nasirova had not only a clear and bell-like voice, but also the ability to listen and hear from the heart. Her sharp breath, logical accents, extremely delicate jingles, modesty and expression characteristic of Uzbek women delight and surprise the listeners.

Halima Nosirova started her career in the Uzbek State Model Traveling Troupe in 1927, performing such roles as Maria Antonovna (N. Gogol "The Auditor"), Malikai Turandot (K. Gossi "Malikai Turandot"). From 1929 to 1939,

he worked as a leading singer of the Uzbek State Musical Theater and from 1939 to 1986, the opera and ballet theater named after A. Navoi until the end of his life. Halima Nosirova, who has a unique, unique juicy wide-range voice, stage talent, "Khalima" (G'. Zafari), "Arshin mal-alan" (U. Khojibekov), "Layli and Majnun" (Khurshid; music by T. Sodikov), He gained fame among our people by playing the main roles in musical performances such as "Farhod and Shirin" (Khurshid; music by V. Uspensky), "Gulsara" (K. Yashin and M. Muhammedov; music by R. Glier).

Halima Nosirova's success on the stage of the musical drama theater gave impetus to the emergence of Uzbek opera performance. E. staged in 1938 at the Uzbek Musical Theater. The character of Akjunus in Brusilovsky's opera "Er Tagin" was the artist's first opera role. Halima Nosirova is the first performer of the first Uzbek operas ¹ :

1. M. Ashrafiy and S. Vasilenko. The opera "The Tempest" (1939), Nargul party.
2. T. Sodikov and R. Glier. The opera "Layli and the Madman" (1940), Layli's aria.
3. T. Jalilov and V. Brotsin. "Tahir and Zuhra" opera (1949), Zuhra aria.
4. R. Glier and T. Sodikov. Opera "Gulsara" (1949) managed to integrate national singing art with opera performance in the Gulsara party.²

Later, this situation became the main feature of the interpretation of all the roles created by Halima Nosirova. He created his first comic character on the stage of Uzbek opera in the interpretation of the main character in the opera "Maysara's Work" by the great creator, highly skilled composer Sulaymon Yudakov. Maysara's lyrical and comic situations were convincingly demonstrated. We can clearly observe this in Maysara's aria from the opera. If we say that the opera was really written for Halimakhanim Nosirova, we will be telling the truth.

¹ B. Nasriddinov. Halima Nosirova. (Monography) Tashkent.: 1983

² T. E. Solomonova. History of Uzbek music. Tashkent.: 1981

Майсара: *mf*

Ёл - физ - ли - гим хам бе - ва - лик муш-кул э - кан

бу мун - ча - лик.

3

If the vocal part in the aria is of particular importance, the Maysara part in the opera is reflected in the musical score of Uzbek national melodies and laments. It should be noted that Halima Nosirova is a unique performer of Uzbek national anthems and songs.

"...I learned Uzbek tunes and songs, statuses from our favorite hafiz and master musicians Mulla Toychi Tashmukhammedov, Khoji Abdulaziz, Muhyiddin Qori Yaqubov, Domla Halim Ibodov, Yusufjan Kheun, Usta Olim Komilov, Abduqadir Ismailov, Akhmadjon Umurzakov, Madrahim Sherozi," he says. Halima Nosirova⁴.

Uzbek classical music plays a major role in the concert repertoire of the owner of a unique voice. In particular, status tracks such as "Ushshok", "Dugoh", "Chorgoh", "Samarkand ushshok", "Chapandozi Navo", folk song "Chaman ichra", "Uzganча" adapted for voice and symphony orchestra by A. Kozlovsky, "Gulyuz" ichra", "Figon" and especially the lyrical-dramatic aspect of the songs "Tanovor" deepened in the performance of Halima Nosirova. "I am an Uzbek

³ С.Юдаков. "Майсаранинг иши" опера (клавир) Тошкент.: 1985 й.

⁴ С.Маннопов. Навобахш оҳанглар.Тошкент.: 2018. 89 б.

girl", "Mehnat ahli" (together with F. Borukhonova in a big song), "Voice of an Uzbek girl" (M. Leviev), "Welcome" (S. Jalil) sang the songs of such composers in an upbeat spirit.

In the artist's opinion, a song is a constant companion in a person's daily life and life. People's favorite artist Halima Nosirova expressed her reaction to the important changes and updates of her time. He organized various concert programs on the battlefields in order to raise the morale of our people and the soldiers of our country during the terrible years of the terrible war, during the construction of the large Ferghana, Tashkent, Logan, Chirchik canals, Kattakurgan water reservoir, Farkhod hydroelectric power plant, in the development of the Mirzachol, Karshi, Jizzakh deserts. The artist created various characters in the films "Honey", "Gift from the Front", "Maftuningman" filmed at the "Uzbekfilm" film studio and also made a significant contribution to the cinematography.

A number of foreign critics who were impressed by Halima Nosirova's brilliant art and talent gave her a high rating. In 1956, the newspapers "Lison ash-shaab" published in Syria and "Statesman" published in India expressed their sincere opinions about the Uzbek singer's extremely pleasant and attractive voice that soothes the hearts. His nightingale voice as an Uzbek artist has spread in dozens of countries such as India, Burma, Lebanon, Egypt, Iran, China, and Canada. In his lifetime, he established a statue of himself with two remarkable aspects. One is his truly folk art, and the other is his great happiness with his students and followers.

In the last century, her elegant and charming voice, the strange delicacy of her voice, her ability to instantly take the listener from grass to water, from water to grass, gave her a special charm, made the singer known and famous among the people over the years. Regrettably, the promotion and campaigning of this human creativity in the coming years is certainly not as positive as we thought. This year marks the 106th anniversary of the artist's birth, and for some reason, cultural

events dedicated to the bright star of our opera art have not yet appeared on the screen. If we approach the issue objectively, isn't there an opportunity to put into practice the educational-methodical collection and textbooks, audio-video samples compiled on the basis of the memory books of the art representatives who are considered to be the founders of our opera, and the musical masterpieces of Uzbek and world nations performed by them? In the comprehensive education of the young generation, it is necessary to show our nation the art form of opera, which is considered to be the golden age of our musical art.

At the present time, followers of highly talented people are appearing on the Uzbek stage with their bright voices. Bright representatives of Uzbek art such as Muyassar Razzokova, Saida Mamadalieva, Zamira Suyunova, Munojot Yolchieva, Nasiba Sattorova, Matluba Dadaboeva, Nasiba Abdullaeva, (deceased) Dilnura Kadirjonova, Komila Borieva, Mahfuza Karimova, Nodira Pirmatova are truly the star of Uzbek opera and singing art like Halima Nosirova. worthy followers. As a worthy follower of the teacher, the above-mentioned stars of our art are achieving a number of scientific and practical researches and successes in the field of creativity.

REFERENCES

1. Jan. Pecker. "Uzbeksaya Opera". Moscow: 1984
2. B. Nasriddinov. Halima Nosirova. (Monography) Tashkent:. 1983
3. T.E. Solomonova. History of Uzbek music. Tashkent:. 1981
4. S. Mannopov. Navobakhsh tones. Tashkent:. 2018: 89 p.
5. S. Yudakov. "Maysara's work" opera (piano) Tashkent:. 1985
6. M. Achildiyeva 2021 Academic Yunus Rajabi and His Scientific Heritage Annals of Romanian Society for Cell Biology 25(4) 9092-9100
7. Achildiyeva M, Khojimamatov A, Ikromova F (2022) Shashmaqom lessons: about the status of "Navo". INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT RESEARCH 11(01) 55-58

8. Achildiyeva M, Ikromova F (2021) ABOUT MAHMUDJON TOJIBOYEVS PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) 9(5) 240-244
9. Achildiyeva M, Ikromova F (2021) TANBUR ONE OF ANCIENT INSTRUMENTS GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) 9(6) 302-308
10. www. Sharq taronalari.uz internet network
11. Achildiyeva M, Ikromova F (2022) CHOIR ART IN UZBEKISTAN BOTIR UMIDJONOV (EURASIAN JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES 7 54-56
12. Achildiyeva M, Ikromova F (2021) “The third renaissance towards ascending” EUROPEAN SCHOLAR JOURNAL “An open access, peer reviewed multidisciplinary journal” 2 (9) 17-20
13. Maxfuzakhon Karimova, Muyassarkhon Achildiyeva, Farangiz Ikromova (2021) USE FROM PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC LESSONS EUROPEAN SCHOLAR JOURNAL “An open access, peer reviewed multidisciplinary journal” 2 (4) 460-463
14. Achildiyeva M, Xojimatov A, Yuldasheva D, Ikromova F (2021) Uyghur Folk Singing Genre Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry 12 (10) 3510-3515
15. Usmanova, D., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN THE UZBEK.
16. Qizi, S. G. N. (2022). ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN THE UZBEK. *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 812-816.
17. Komilova, N. A. Comparative Analysis of “Gender” Concept and Issues of Gender Field in English and Uzbek Languages. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 5(6), 2191-2194.
18. Shodiyeva, G. N. K., & Dustmatov, H. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 234-237.

19. qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINCIPILES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).
20. Тухтаева, К. Д. (2020). SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF THE PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF THE ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES WITH THE NAMES OF VEGETABLES AND FRUITS. *ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ*, (SI-3).